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PREDICTION OF OBSETRIC BLOOD LOSS IN WOMEN WITH PRETERM BIRTH (LITERATURE REVIEW)

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ABSTRACT

Recently, vascular and hemodynamic disorders in the mother, which are observed in various somatic diseases, have traditionally been attributed to risk factors for preterm birth. At the heart of violations of hemodynamics and microcirculation, including in the uteroplacental pool, developing with preeclampsia and various somatic pathologies, is a generalized dysfunction of the endothelium. It is extremely important to study the content in the blood of pregnant women with premature birth of indicators of the anticoagulant potential of the blood, in particular, the content of the main anticoagulant, antithrombin III. In preterm birth, its amount was 85.15 ± 5.31 mg/l, which is significantly lower than in women with a physiological course of pregnancy, which indicates the important role of antithrombin III deficiency in the development of these severe pregnancy complications.

Keywords: endothelial dysfunction, blood lose, somatic pathology, preterm birth, pregnancy.

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ПРОГНОЗИРОВАНИЕ АКУШЕРСКОЙ КРОВОПОТЕРИ У ЖЕНЩИН С ПРЕЖДЕВРЕМЕННЫМИ РОДАМИ

АННОТАЦИЯ

В последнее время сосудистые и гемодинамические нарушения у матери, наблюдаемые при различных соматических заболеваниях, традиционно относят к факторам риска преждевременных родов. В основе нарушений гемодинамики и микроциркуляции, в том числе в маточно-плацентарном бассейне, развивающихся при преэклампсии и различной соматической патологии, лежит генерализованная дисфункция эндотелия. Чрезвычайно важным является изучение содержания в крови беременных с преждевременными родами показателей антикоагулянтного потенциала крови, в особенности содержания основного антикоагулянта - антитромбина III. При преждевременных родах его количество составило $85,15 \pm 5,31$ мг/л, что значительно ниже, чем у женщин с физиологическим течением беременности, что свидетельствует о важной роли дефицита антитромбина III в развитии этих тяжелых осложнений беременности.

Ключевые слова: эндотелиальная дисфункция, кровопотеря, соматическая патология, преждевременные роды, беременность.

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MUDDATDAN OLDIN TUG'GAN AYOLLARDA AKUSHERLIK QON YO'QOTISHLARINI BASHORAT QILISH (ADABIYOTLAR SHARHI)

ANNOTATSIYA

So'nggi paytlarda turli xil somatik kasalliklarda kuzatiladigan onadagi qon tomir va gemodinamik buzilishlar an'anaviy ravishda erta tug'ilish uchun xavf omillariga bog'liq. Gemodinamika va mikrosirkulyatsiyaning buzilishi, shu jumladan preeklampsi va turli xil somatik patologiyalar bilan rivojlanayotgan uteroplasental hovuzda endoteliyning umumiy disfunktsiyasi mavjud. Erta tug'ilgan homilador ayollar qonining antikoagulyant potentsiali ko'rsatkichlarini, xususan, asosiy antikoagulyant, antitrombin III tarkibini o'rganish juda muhimdir. homiladorlikning fiziologik kursi bo'lgan ayollar, bu og'ir homiladorlik asoratlarini rivojlanishida antitrombin III etishmovchiligining muhim rolini ko'rsatadi.

Kalit so'zlar: endotelial disfunktsiya, qon yo'qotish, somatik patologiya, erta tug'ilish, homiladorlik.

The state of the problem of pathological blood loss after premature birth

Postpartum hemorrhage is the main cause of maternal morbidity and mortality worldwide and can be caused by multiple etiologies. The distinction between the different etiologies that lead to PRK and the identification of high-risk signs are crucial for the implementation of effective clinical management. Postpartum bleeding is the main direct cause of maternal morbidity and mortality in women in many countries of the world. Postpartum bleeding is often defined as the loss of > 500 ml of blood after vaginal delivery or > 1000 ml after cesarean section within 24 hours (Nigussie J, Girma B, Molla A.2022).

As reflected in the literature, complications arising during pregnancy, postpartum hemorrhage (PRG) is the most serious complication and the most critically important cause during pregnancy and

childbirth. Postpartum hypotonic bleeding in 70% is the cause of obstetric bleeding, 20% is due to placental abruption, damage to the birth canal, rupture of the uterus, approximately 10% refers to the rotation of the placenta and disruption of its separation and 1% - coagulopathy. The main causes of bleeding, which establish such statistical indicators as maternal and perinatal morbidity and mortality, include: placental abruption, placental presentation and disorders in the hemostasis system. This can cause severe anemia, acute respiratory distress syndrome (ARDS), acute renal failure (ARF), coma and cardiac arrest. Uterine atony, preserved tissue, rupture of the genital tract, clotting problem and rupture of the uterus are the most common causes of postpartum hemorrhage. In developing countries, PCR is one of the leading causes of maternal mortality, accounting for 25-43% of maternal mortality (WHO, 2018).

According to the World Health Organization (WHO), approximately 295,000 women died during pregnancy or after childbirth in 2017. The vast majority of these deaths (94%) occurred in resource-limited settings, and most of them could have been prevented. Most maternal complications develop during pregnancy, and many of them can be prevented or cured. Complications such as maternal obesity, curettage during a previous pregnancy, hypertension, hemoglobin (Hb) levels below or equal to 10 g/dl may exist before pregnancy and may cause problems during pregnancy leading to PRK, especially if they are not treated as part of a woman's care. The definition of primary postpartum hemorrhage (PRK) as the main cause of maternal mortality and severe morbidity has evolved over time to help identify people most prone to morbidity and, consequently, to take timely health measures.

Martynenko P.G., Volkov V.G. (2012) The severity of the contingent of women with early preterm labor is evidenced by the high frequency of their operative delivery and forced obstetric hysterectomy operations during all years. Thus, according to the average annual indicator for 5 years, the frequency of hysterectomy during pregnancy termination in women with a gestation period of 22-27 weeks is 18.6 times higher than in childbirth (28.4) per 1,000 abortions at 22-27 weeks versus 1.53 per 1,000 births at 28 weeks or more. The frequency of small caesarean section (307.0 per 1 thousand abortions in the period of 22-27 weeks according to the average annual indicator for 2008-2012) are 1.4 times higher than in the period of 28 weeks or more (219.2 per 1 thousand births) - with a higher mortality rate in small pregnancy. The rate of complications during small caesarean section is 0.55 per 100 operations, which is higher than at 28 weeks or more (0.35).

The works of many Russian researchers have shown an increased risk of maternal mortality associated with premature birth. Thus, the leading causes of death of women during premature birth were gestosis -26.6%, extragenital diseases - 23.4%, bleeding - 21.9% and sepsis - 12.4%. In the group of women who died during timely delivery, bleeding (25.8%) took the first place among the causes of death, sepsis (22.3%) took the second place, uterine rupture (18.2%) took the third place, extragenital diseases (9.9%) took the fourth place [Tokova Z.Z. et al.].

According to Rostov scientists (Galushchenko E.M. et al. 2020), in women with anomalies of placental attachment, typical blood loss ranges from 3000 to 5000 ml. Placenta previa and ingrowth increase the risk of massive bleeding with subsequent hysterectomy by up to 51%. The number of pathological placentations increases annually by 15.6%. The number of cesarean sections is growing every year, and the risk of this complication increases accordingly. The leading place among the causes of maternal death is occupied by bleeding with premature detachment of the normally located placenta (PPRP), amounting to 20-45.1%, which occurs suddenly in 20.0% of cases before 32 weeks and in 80.0% of patients at 34-37 weeks or more. Bleeding in PPRP is 1.5 times more likely to end with antenatal fetal death, 1.6 times with asphyxia of newborns. Patients with PPRP are 3.0 times more likely to develop hemorrhagic shock, renal and respiratory insufficiency, posthemorrhagic anemia and DIC syndrome.

Briley A, Seed PT, Tydeman G. (2014) Severe diseases associated with postpartum bleeding (PRK) include anemia and the need for blood transfusion, disseminated intravascular coagulation, hysterectomy, and renal or hepatic insufficiency. Women who develop PRK may also suffer from complications, including: liver failure, acute respiratory distress syndrome, the need for open surgery, the need for intensive care, disseminated intravascular coagulation, hysterectomy and cardiac arrest.

With moderate complications, PRK can lead to minor anemia, fatigue, depression and separation anxiety. Interest in PRK is mainly focused on the assessment of its risk factors, prevention and treatment.

According to the Lancet magazine (2021), miscarriage is usually defined as the loss of pregnancy to viability. It is estimated that 23 million miscarriages occur worldwide every year, resulting in 44 pregnancy losses every minute. The combined risk of miscarriage is 15.3% (95% CI 12.5-18.7 %) of all recognized pregnancies. The prevalence in the population of women who have suffered one miscarriage is 10.8% (10.3-11.4%), two miscarriages – 1.9% (1.8-2.1%), and three or more miscarriages – 0.7% (0.5-0.8%). Risk factors for miscarriage include very young or elderly women (under 20 and over 35), elderly men (over 40), very low or very high body mass index, black ethnicity, previous miscarriages, smoking, alcohol, stress, night shifts, air pollution and exposure to pesticides. The consequences of miscarriage are both physical, such as bleeding or infection, and psychological. Psychological consequences include an increased risk of anxiety, depression, post-traumatic stress disorder, and suicide. Miscarriage, and especially repeated miscarriage, is also a marker of the risk of obstetric complications, including premature birth, fetal growth restriction, placental abruption and stillbirth in future pregnancies, as well as a predictor of long-term health problems such as cardiovascular diseases and venous thromboembolism. (Anderson R, Daher S, Regan L.2021)

According to studies (Harrison MS, Muldrow M, Kirub E.2021), mothers who had prolonged labor had a 5 times higher chance of postpartum bleeding compared to normal delivery times. A similar conclusion was obtained from studies conducted in China [Liu C-N, Yu F-B, Xu Y-Z 2021], Pakistan [Gani N, Ali TS. 2013] and Cameroon [Halle-Ekane GE, Emade FK 2015]. This may be due to the fact that prolonged labor causes uterine atony, which is the leading cause of postpartum hemorrhage. This meta-analysis also showed that the probability of postpartum hemorrhage among mothers who did not have prenatal follow-up was 9 times higher than their counterparts. This may be due to the fact that mothers can receive adequate information about institutional childbirth, as well as about the readiness for childbirth and the reddening of complications during visits (prenatal care) to the ANC, which can reduce the risk of postpartum bleeding.

According to the American College of Obstetricians and Gynecologists, PRK leads to cumulative blood loss of ≥ 1000 ml or is characterized by the presence of symptoms of hypovolemia associated with blood loss within 24 hours after vaginal or cesarean section. Treatment of first-line PRK includes pharmacological measures, intrauterine tamponade, ligation of uterine arteries and compression sutures of the uterus; uterine artery embolization (UAE) is performed for women with refractory severe PRK. There are additional important secondary consequences of hemorrhage, which include respiratory distress syndrome in adults, shock, disseminated intravascular coagulation, acute renal failure, loss of fertility and pituitary necrosis (Sheehan syndrome). Hemorrhage, which leads to blood transfusion, is the leading cause of severe maternal morbidity in the United States, followed by disseminated intravascular coagulation. In the United States, the incidence of postpartum bleeding increased by 26% between 1994 and 2006, mainly due to an increase in atony rates. On the contrary, maternal mortality from postpartum obstetric hemorrhage has decreased since the late 1980s and amounted to just over 10% of maternal mortality (approximately 1.7 deaths per 100,000 live births) in 2009 (Committee on Practice Bulletins-Obstetrics 2017).

Thus, the problem of preterm birth requires a multilateral study and an integrated approach to its solution with an emphasis on perinatal outcomes as the main criterion for evaluating the effectiveness of prolongation of pregnancy and tactics of delivery of a premature fetus.

The main risk factors for massive blood loss in women with premature birth.

Postpartum hemorrhage (PPH) remains a major global burden contributing to high maternal mortality and morbidity rates. The assessment of risk factors for PRK should be carried out in the antenatal, intranatal and postpartum periods for the timely prevention of maternal morbidity and mortality associated with PRK.

Bazirete O, Nzayirambaho M, Umubyeyi A. (2022) Uterine atony remains the main cause of primary PRK. Along with other established risk factors for PRK, prenatal bleeding and intrauterine

fetal death should be included as risk factors in the development and validation of PRK prediction models. Large-scale studies are needed to further study the potential risk factors of PRK.

Kljakić D, Milosavljević MZ, Jovanović M. (2020) authors from Serbia describe a case of placental infection of *S. marcescens* described as the cause of extremely premature birth and loss of infants during pregnancy with twins due to pneumonitis followed by respiratory failure. Infections as risk factors during pregnancy are complex and important because infection affects not only the mother, but also the fetus. The duration and results of infection depend on the number and virulence of microbes, the immunobiological characteristics of the mother, the method of infection spread and the gestational period. The immunobiological status of the mother is stressed, taking into account the suppressed function of T-lymphocytes and frequent compositional changes in the biological flora in the birth canal during pregnancy, which significantly contributes to the development of infections. As a result of infections during pregnancy, the fetal membranes can become infected (chorioamnionitis and intraamniotic infection syndrome), which leads to premature placental abruption and spontaneous miscarriage or premature birth. Due to the very high infant mortality in these conditions, the perinatal morbidity of the mother is also high. According to these findings, *Serratia* bacteremia has a high mortality rate of approximately 37% within six months. During pregnancy, this infection is a rare but potentially fatal disorder that is also associated with chorioamnionitis or placental abscess, miscarriages and premature birth. The authors describe a clinical case. A 26-year-old, Rh-negative, childbearing mother with a Rh-positive partner undergoing a regularly monitored second pregnancy of a dichorion twin was the subject of the study. The patient was hospitalized at 24 + 5 WG with scant vaginal bleeding, abdominal pain and body temperature up to 37.5 ° C. Gynecological examination revealed bleeding within the dilatation of the cervix with a diameter of 1 cm near the cervix. Laboratory tests revealed leukocytosis with elevated C-reactive protein (CRP) ($28.3 \times 10^9/L$ white blood cells (leukocytes), $3.50 \times 10^9/L$ erythrocytes (erythrocytes), 108 g/l hemoglobin (Hgb), $385 \times 10^9/l$ platelets (PLT) and 28.5 mg/l CRP. Other laboratory analyses were in the range with reference values. Treatment was started with intravenous administration of ceftriaxone at a dose of 2 g / day. After admission, the fetal membranes spontaneously ruptured, and extremely premature birth of a female twin occurred at 25 + 0 weeks of gestation. Both babies died two days after giving birth. Pathological and microbiological analyses revealed chorioamnionitis caused by *S. marcescens*. According to the antibiotic chart, antibiotic treatment continued for the next 7 days. Examination of samples of discharge from the cervix and vagina was negative three days and two weeks after therapy. *S. marcescens* can cause spontaneous miscarriages and, in this important case, cause the loss of discordant twins in extremely premature delivery by an immunocompetent patient. Infection with *S. marcescens* cannot be excluded as a cause of discordant growth and should be confirmed by further studies.

The Russian authors (Kravchenko Yu.P. et al. 2018) analyze in their article the etiological risk factors of massive obstetric bleeding. In the course of the study, the researchers found combined forms of risk factors for acute massive blood loss: placenta previa in combination with a scar on the uterus after cesarean section and conservative myomectomy, intrauterine interventions in the anamnesis, hypertensive disorders, preeclampsia and thrombophilia.

Ola Didrik Zaugstad (2012) A well-known neonatologist, author of a study in the field of problems concerning newborns and premature babies, Ola Didrik Zaugstad believes that today not enough is known about the causes of premature birth. At the same time, he notes the following causes of premature birth: bleeding during pregnancy, stress, pregnancy complications, hard physical work, cervical weakness, multiple births, early discharge of water, heredity.

Serova O. F., Sedaya L. V. et al (2018) A significant risk factor for placenta accretion is pregnancy with implantation in the scar area after CS. Useful parameters for ultrasound monitoring in relation to the risk of prenatal bleeding and early CS include the length of the cervix of 25 mm or less, the distance between the inner pharynx and the edge of the placenta of 20 mm or less, the thickness of the edge of the placenta of 10 mm or less. At a distance from the inner pharynx to the edge of the placenta <10 mm, the risk of prenatal bleeding is significantly greater than at a distance from the inner pharynx to the edge of the placenta of 11-20 mm [odds ratio (OR) = 11.5; 95%

confidence interval (CI) 1.6-76.7], the frequency of early COP is higher (73-91 vs. 24-40%). Shortening of the cervix to 25 mm or less with a low placenta location is associated with an increase in the frequency of prenatal bleeding (75 compared to 31%; $p=0.02$), the need for hemo transfusion (25 compared to 3%; $p=0.02$), lower weight.

Modern features of risk factors for obstetric bleeding are that the following trends are increasingly observed: the frequency of bleeding associated with preeclampsia, HELLP syndrome, premature placental abruption, placenta previa, fetal loss syndromes with hematogenous thrombophilia increases, this indicates the relationship between violations of the trophoblast invasion and placentation with hereditary and acquired forms of hemostasis disorders.

Markers of the study of functional vascular endothelium and trigger mechanisms leading to pathological blood loss

In order to understand the causes and earlier treatment of premature birth, rather than their consequences, the question of introducing markers of premature birth into clinical practice is being acutely raised. It is known that premature birth is accompanied by an imbalance of pro- and anti-angiogenic factors, which is, apparently, the result of the activity of certain alleles. With the progress of molecular biology, it became possible to isolate the DNA of almost any protein from biological fluids (amniotic fluid, urine, cervical mucus, vaginal secretions, serum, plasma, saliva) using a polymerase chain reaction. An attempt is being made to find molecular predictors of premature development of labor activity, which will make it possible to choose a rational etiopathogenetically justified therapy.

Currently, there are no known biomarkers for antenatal screening of coronary heart disease, despite the fact that it is one of the most common congenital birth defects. Clinical strategies for the diagnosis of coronary heart disease mainly depend on fetal echocardiography, which is often limited in resources and offered only to high-risk mothers. According to a multicenter study conducted in China, despite the high specificity of fetal echocardiography at 99.8%, the sensitivity was much lower, only 33.9%.

Chen L, Xiu Y, Wu Q (2022) Maternal serum Lamin A is a potential biomarker that can predict adverse pregnancy outcomes. The maternal alpha-fetoprotein serum (AFP) test was first introduced into clinical practice for screening fetal neural tube defects (NTD) in the 1970s. Since then, various other methods of prenatal screening tests have been developed, but screening tests using pregnancy-related biomarkers in maternal peripheral blood have been recognized as one of the best methods of prenatal diagnosis because they help to avoid invasive tests such as amniocentesis and cordocentesis. Moreover, these tests can be performed even in primary hospitals, which can then help in deciding whether a patient needs a referral for further prenatal evaluation. A prospective screening study was conducted on singleton pregnancies at 15-18 weeks of pregnancy. After a routine test for alpha-fetoprotein (AFP), chorionic gonadotropin (hCG) and unconjugated estriol (uE3), serum LMNA levels were measured. The serum LMNA levels were then converted to multiple medians (MoM). Median MoM values for adverse pregnancy outcomes were compared with those for normal pregnancy. For diseases with differential expression of LMNA, a different cohort of case-control was recruited in a prospective study. Further, the diagnostic value of LMNA in these diseases was evaluated. In the period from January 1, 2017 to June 30, 2018, a total of 2,906 single pregnancies were recruited. Out of 2,906 cases, 2,711 had data available for analysis. Congenital structural abnormalities, chromosomal abnormalities and obstetric complications were observed in 152 (5.6%), 15 (0.6%) and 278 (10.3%) patients, respectively. LMNA was reduced in pregnancies with intrauterine coronary artery disease, fetal neural tube defects (NTD) and preeclampsia (PE). The cohort of the case-control study included 256 IHD, 60 DNT, 67 PE and 400 normal pregnancies. The areas under the curve for prenatal diagnoses of CHD, ZTB and PE were 0.875, 0.871 and 0.816, respectively.

The authors found that LMNA was significantly reduced in all subgroups of coronary artery disease, with the exception of pulmonary stenosis and vascular ring groups. In addition, the GA range of fetuses included in this study ranged from 12 to 35 weeks; and our results showed that coronary heart disease can be predicted by maternal serum LMNA levels as early as the first trimester. If the

LMNA test can be added to the serum screening of the first or second trimester, serological screening of coronary heart disease can be enhanced, which will allow earlier detection of coronary heart disease. AFP has been a traditional diagnostic biomarker in the prenatal diagnosis of DNT, but its false-positive level is high. According to one study from China, the positive prognostic value of AFP for the diagnosis of DNT was only 16.2%.²⁴ In recent years, several studies have been conducted to identify new markers of DNT, but none of them have been translated into clinical applications.²⁵ See,²⁶ In this study, the diagnostic accuracy of LMNA for NTD prediction was higher than that of AFP, and their combination significantly improved diagnostic efficiency (AUC, 0.990). In addition, the diagnosis of DNT Using LMNA was not affected by subtypes. The application of the LMNA test to serum screening performed in the first or second trimester and combination with AFP may ultimately improve the diagnostic accuracy of NTD.

Prognosis and prevention of bleeding in women with premature birth

Obstetric hemorrhages, despite the global measures implemented in the world to prevent them, still pose a real threat to the health and life of the mother, require the search for more effective measures for their prevention and treatment. Obstetric bleeding that occurs during pregnancy, childbirth and the postpartum period remains one of the main problems of practical obstetrics. Quite often in the practice of an obstetrician-gynecologist, bleeding occurs after delivery and is considered hypotonic. In the developing countries of the world, massive blood loss is dominant in the structure of maternal mortality. There are many conflicting points of view on the genesis of massive obstetric bleeding. In modern conditions, methods of organ-preserving technologies have been developed.

The structure of obstetric bleeding is dominated by PPRP and hypotonic bleeding. Massive bleeding developed during operative delivery, the presence of a scar on the uterus after cesarean section and pregnancy complications: anemia, large fetus and polyhydramnios. In modern conditions, the introduction of recombinant factor VII is recommended, the effect of which outstrips the effectiveness of the use of SPP by 30 minutes. Prevention of obstetric bleeding in the high-risk group (RCOG, 2009) consists in intraoperative administration of carbetocin in the presence of a scar on the uterus, placenta previa, placental abruption, large fetus, uterine fibroids. It is necessary to perform a step-by-step surgical hemostasis: applying a compression suture by Lynch. High-risk patients should be delivered as planned. Delivery should be accompanied by intraoperative reinfusion of autohomologous erythrocytes with presentation and detachment of a normally located placenta, a scar on the uterus and expansion of the volume of surgical intervention, scientists N.I. Kan, A.S. Lillepeo, N.G. Teterina (2017) came to this conclusion.

Conclusion of the literary review

Thus, obstetric bleeding remains relevant to the present time, requires continued research that expands the understanding of their etiopathogenesis, the possibilities of prediction, prevention and treatment. Modern realities allow us to consolidate international scientific and clinical experience in studying the features, differences in measures for the prevention and treatment of obstetric bleeding, which will allow us to modify (update) modern clinical protocols, adapt them to modern conditions. The wide opportunity available today for open access to data from the world databases of clinical and scientific research allows you to remotely get acquainted with the most modern trends in the prognosis and prevention of obstetric bleeding, study their effectiveness, and implement the knowledge gained into real practice. Researchers aim to prevent postpartum bleeding by rejecting unjustified induction and stimulation of labor, unjustified amniotomy, prohibited benefits and caesarean section only for strict indications.

Overview on the topic: "Prediction and prevention of obstetric bleeding in preterm labor" was prepared on the basis of databases: EBSCOhost, Springer NATURE, Scopus, PubMed, Google Scholar, eLibrary for the period from 2012-2022.

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